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AUTHOR:	Utkur Djanibekov, Ana Gonzalez-Martinez, Georgios Miaris, Anke M. Herrmann, Albert von Ow, Sonja G. Keel
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Abstract

This study analyses how dietary changes can impact nitrogen inputs to and losses from the soil through changes in agricultural production including changes in crop area, livestock numbers, foreign trade and manure application for crops. We present two case studies: (1) all countries of the European Union (EU) and (2) Switzerland. For the EU level case study which focuses on a reduction in meat consumption, we rely on the outcomes of a literature review and on previous work undertaken by the Agriculture Member State Modelling (AGMEMOD) and MITERRA modelling teams in the context of the H2020 SUPREMA (Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture) project. For the case of Switzerland effects of healthier diets are quantified using the Swiss sustainable food systems (SWISSfoodSys) model.

The results of the European Union case study show that the dietary changes reduce livestock numbers, production and prices of animal-based products. The reduction of livestock numbers also decreases GHG emissions, and these impacts differ across regions. The results of the Swiss case study show that dietary changes impact the entire food system including agricultural production, processing and trade. A substantial consumption shift towards vegetables, fruits and grains is observed, while the consumption of meat and alcoholic beverages is substantially lower. These changes increase the area where grains, vegetables and fruits are grown, while the area of fodder crops (i.e. feed like silage maize) and meadows are smaller. As a result of lower feed availability, total livestock number is reduced, leading to lower amounts of manure. Both case studies demonstrate the direct link between changes in diets and nitrogen availability. We conclude that moving towards healthier diets including lower meat consumption would be an effective approach to reduce nitrogen losses.

Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	5
List of Figures.....	5
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Case of the EU	6
2.1. Background.....	6
2.2. Bringing together production and consumption of animal products in the EU.....	7
2.3. Historical trends of red meat production at Member State level.....	9
2.4. Expected developments in the medium-term	12
2.5. Selected studies.....	13
2.6. Quantifying the impacts of a dietary change in the EU.....	14
2.7. Additional insights at Member State level	19
3. Case of Switzerland	20
3.1. Methods	20
3.2. Results	21
4. Conclusions.....	28
5. Future research	28
List of references.....	29

List of Tables

Table 1. Literature review – assumptions included in previous studies modelling the impacts of dietary changes on emissions.	14
Table 2. Red meat (apparent) consumption trends in EU, 2008-2018.	15
Table 3. Comparison of red meat (apparent) consumption patterns in EU, 2008-2018.	16
Table 4. Results at EU28 level (% deviation from baseline in 2030).	17
Table 5. Results at EU28 level (% deviation from baseline in 2030).	18
Table 6. Emissions EU28 (% deviation from baseline in 2030).....	18
Table 7. Impacts on food consumption and related production effects in the Netherlands.....	20

List of Figures

Figure 1. Meat self-sufficiency rate in the European Union (EU-28), by type of meat (2000-2015).	8
Figure 2. EU self-sufficiency rates for selected animal products and fish.....	8
Figure 3. Cumulative annual pig meat production by EU-27 MS, (1970-2023).	9
Figure 4. Cumulative annual beef meat production by EU-27 MS, (1968-2023).	10
Figure 5. Cumulative annual sheep and goat meat production by EU-27 MS, (1975-2023).....	11
Figure 6. EU27 Meat consumption per capita (right axis, bars) and EU27 domestic use (left axis, blue line), (2005-2035).	13
Figure 7. EU27 meat production and domestic use (right axis) and EU27 meat net trade (left axis), (2005-2035).	13
Figure 8. Share (%) of vegetarian and vegan population (2018 vs 2030).	16
Figure 9. Changes (%) in consumption per capita (2018 vs 2030).	17
Figure 10. GHG emission agriculture (% change compared to baseline).	19
Figure 11. Schematic description of the SWISSfoodSys model.	21
Figure 12. Food consumption in the reference and diet change scenarios.	22
Figure 13. Agricultural land use in the reference and diet change scenarios.	23
Figure 14. Crop area in the reference and diet change scenarios.	24
Figure 15. Livestock number in the reference and diet change scenarios.....	25
Figure 16. Food trade, domestic production and consumption in nutritional energy value in the reference and diet change scenarios.	26
Figure 17. Manure application to crops (a) and supply of manure by livestock types (b).....	27

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AGMEMOD	Agriculture Member State Modelling
EU	European Union
SUPREMA	Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture
SWISSfoodSys	Swiss sustainable food systems
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The current food production and consumption systems have substantial impacts on the environment and human health (Tilman and Clark, 2014; Rieger et al., 2022). Global food production emits about one third of total greenhouse gases (GHG; Crippa et al., 2021; Tubiello et al., 2021), pollute water resources with agricultural chemicals, and result in biodiversity loss (Tilman et al., 2001). Animal products are the main source of GHG emissions in food systems and are a major driver of deforestation and biodiversity loss (IPCC, 2019). On average, Europeans consume about 800 kcal/day of animal-based products (FAO, 2020), which is above nutritional recommendations and above an environmentally sustainable amount (Willett et al., 2019).

Dietary changes directly influence environmental pollution, agricultural production and human health. For example, the study by Stylianou et al. (2021) showed that substituting 10% of daily calorie intake from beef and processed meat by vegetables, fruits, nuts, legumes and seafood can reduce dietary GHG emissions by 33%. The impacts of dietary shifts can differ for countries, regions and farm types. Rieger et al. (2022) using modelling approaches showed that the agricultural sector of 27 European Union countries could benefit from a dietary change. However, impacts differ across regions. In regions that specialise on animal farming incomes decrease, while in regions that specialise on vegetable and fruit production incomes increase. With projected changes in population diets (Kearney, 2010), it is important to understand the impacts of dietary changes on agricultural production and environmental outputs.

The objective of this study is to analyse how the change in food consumption can impact nitrogen inputs to and losses from the soil through changes in agricultural production including changes in crop area, livestock numbers, foreign trade and manure application for crops. We present two case studies: (1) all countries of the European Union (EU) and (2) Switzerland. We present here the case of Switzerland because its food consumption accounts for 25% of the total environmental impacts (Nathani et al., 2022).

Regarding the analysis at the EU level, this deliverable relies on the outcomes of a literature review, as well as on previous work undertaken by the Agriculture Member State Modelling (AGMEMOD) and MITERRA modelling teams in the context of the H2020 SUPREMA (Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture) project. More specifically, in the context of SUPREMA, a hypothetical scenario for the period 2020-30 exploring a dietary change in the EU was simulated by means of the modelling system AGMEMOD-MITERRA. For the case study of Switzerland, we analyse changes in food consumption, by simulating a scenario that includes the change in Switzerland until 2030 and compare it against a reference scenario. Here, we use the Swiss sustainable food systems (SWISSfoodSys) model to analyse impacts of dietary changes.

2. Case of the EU

2.1. Background

Citizens in developed economies are increasingly becoming aware of the impacts of unsustainable livestock production and consumption of animal proteins. Drawing attention to the EU case, the RISE Foundation (Buckwell and Nadeu, 2018) states that a dietary change should be a priority in the EU policy agenda since livestock production and consumption are not in their Safe Operating Space (SOS).¹ Pursuing a transition towards a 'healthy' diet with a more balanced animal/plant-based protein intake

¹ Buckwell and Nadeu (2018) defines the EU livestock SOS by using lower boundaries for human nutrition and pasture utilisation and upper boundaries for GHG emissions and nitrogen flows.

is a multi-dimensional phenomenon which should involve all actors in the food system, e.g. consumers, producers, civil society, policy-makers, etc. Similarly, the benefits related to the mentioned dietary change are not limited to public health improvements.² In addition, reductions of atmospheric CO₂ emissions and acidification of soil can be expected, as well as improvements in farm income for those farmers delivering products that can obtain a 'premium' in the market (e. g. organic, local origin, etc.). All these interlinked elements will eventually result in more sustainable systems from economic, environmental and societal perspectives. In order to support this transition in the EU, in 2018 the European Commission published the so-called EU Protein Strategy'.³

Box 1. Defining the Safe Operating Space (SOS) for EU livestock

Buckwell and Nadeu (2018) suggest that bringing the livestock sector into its SOS will involve achieving the following boundaries:

- The dietary lower bound in two-thirds of member states (MS) should be around 80% of current consumption for eggs and 80% to 90% for milk;
- With the exception of Romania, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Latvia and Estonia, in order to utilise all permanent pasture the allowed number of livestock units in all the other Member States should be reduced. In contrast, additional livestock units could be supported when rotational grass (i.e. temporary leys), crop by-products and residues are also taken into account.
- In order to achieve the emissions goals defined in the Paris Agreement, all MS must reduce livestock emissions by between 37% (Bulgaria) and 82% (Cyprus); and
- In terms of N fixation,⁴ a 65% reduction of the fixation would be required at EU level – this implies individual reductions ranging 35% (the Netherlands) to 90% (Ireland).

Source: Buckwell and Nadeu (2018).

2.2. Bringing together production and consumption of animal products in the EU

Looking at the historical evolution of the self-sufficiency rates for different types of meats (Figure 1), the strong focus on meeting the needs of the domestic market is observed. As indicated by Jongeneel et al. (2020), the EU self-sufficiency rates reflect the existing import protection, as well as the fact that the system is not competitive in prices due high production costs (compared to countries like Brazil). Jongeneel et al. (2020) suggest that in the coming years the production of the sector could be closely linked to European consumption since there is very limited scope to direct European meat products to the international market. In the coming decade, it can be expected that the mentioned already 'high' production costs could increase even more when producers try to comply with a stronger environmental regulation, as well as higher animal welfare standards. All these factors could lead to a decline in the size of the EU livestock sector, although the adjustments are expected to follow a heterogenous pattern across EU regions.

² As indicated by the Donau Soja Association Report 'The European Protein Transition, those diets that incorporate more plant protein such as pulses and soy are healthier and more sustainable than the 'standard' EU diet.

³ See, also: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0757>.

⁴ This is calculated based on Gross Nutrient Balance (GNB), population and maximum estimated nitrogen fixation established by the nutrient boundary.

Figure 1. Meat self-sufficiency rate in the European Union (EU-28), by type of meat (2000-2015).

Notes: A value above 100% means that the product is also exported, while values below hundred suggest that product need to be imported since EU production is not sufficient to serve EU demand.

Sources: Reproduced from Statista (2019).

Figure 2. EU self-sufficiency rates for selected animal products and fish.

Source: Reproduced from European Union (2023).

Notes: For animal products, the values correspond to the average for the period 2020-2022, while the average for the period 2020-2021 is reported in the case of fish. SMP stands for 'Skimmed-milk powder'.

Moreover, Figure 2 provides an updated picture of the EU self-sufficiency rates for animal and fish products. As indicated by European Commission (2023), currently EU self-sufficiency rates are above 100% for most types of meats and dairy products, sheep and goat being the only exception. In contrast, the low self-sufficiency rates in the case of fish and seafood indicates a stronger dependence on imports to meet EU needs. Self-sufficiency rates for dairy products have remained stable over the years. Overall, production levels for dairy have been consistently high in order to satisfy domestic demand and, particularly in the case of milk powders (SMP), also to delivering production to international markets (European Commission, 2023).

2.3. Historical trends of red meat production at Member State level

Figure 3 presents the evolution of annual pig meat production in each EU Member State (MS) over the period 1970-2023. The y-axis shows pig meat production in thousand tonnes (carcass weight), while the x-axis displays the relevant year. Each vertical bar represents total pig meat production, with individual production values for each country for a particular year. In order to facilitate visualization, MS are ordered by production volume, with those producing more pig meat at the bottom of the figure and those producing less at the top. Overall, pig meat production in the EU has shown an increasing trend over the years. This increase is partly due to significant production growth in countries like Germany and Spain, and partly due to the expansion of the EU. As new MS joined the EU, their production figures contributed marginally to the overall total, enhancing the upward trend observed in the data. The total upward trend in pig meat production reflects not only the increased volume of pig meat production but also the pig meat availability for consumption in the EU since the measurement regards volumes in slaughterhouses.

In 2021, the figure indicates the highest level of pig meat production in the EU over the 53-year span, exceeding 23,000 thousand tonnes. This peak can be attributed to the increase in pig production of leading producers such as Germany and Spain. However, decline is observed in 2022 and 2023, primarily due to a reduction in pig meat production in Germany. For instance, in 2020 (the last year with the highest pig meat production in Germany across EU), the volume of pig meat production reached 5.112 thousand tonnes in Germany, while in 2023 it reached 4.179. This indicates a reduction of approximately 933 thousand tonnes or 18%. Three MS - Germany, Spain, and France - account for more than 50% of the EU’s pig meat production, which reached a peak of 12.349 thousand tonnes in 2021. In addition, Germany shows the highest production levels in the EU until 2020. Afterwards, Spain placed at the bottom of Figure 3, which indicates the highest in pig meat production in 2021 in EU.

Figure 3. Cumulative annual pig meat production by EU-27 MS, (1970-2023).

Source: Authors’ compilation based on Eurostat, slaughtering in slaughterhouses - monthly data, data code: apro_mt_pwgtm.

Notes: The MS pig production is illustrated ordered. The highest values are at the bottom.

Figure 4. Cumulative annual beef meat production by EU-27 MS, (1968-2023).
 Source: Authors' compilation based on Eurostat, slaughtering in slaughterhouses - monthly data, data code: apro_mt_pwgtm.
 Notes: The MS beef production is illustrated ordered. The highest values are at the bottom. Beef includes the following categories: bull, bullock, calf, cattle young, cow, and heifer. Member State is assigned a unique color across the years.

Figure 4 illustrates the beef (bull, bullock, calf, cattle young, cow, and heifer) meat production in the EU MS over the period spanning from 1968 to 2023. The y-axis denotes beef meat production in thousand tonnes (carcass weight), while the x-axis represents the years. Each bar in the figure portrays the total beef meat production, with distinct production values for each MS for a particular year. As in Figure 3, countries with higher beef meat production are positioned at the bottom of the figure, while those with lower production volumes are located at the top.

Beef meat production (Figure 4) exhibits an increasing trend from 1968 to the beginning of the 1990s. However, since then, there has not been a discernible trend. Notably, in 2018, the highest beef meat production in a span of 55 years was recorded, with a volume slightly exceeding 7000 tonnes. France has consistently been the key player of beef meat in the EU for the past 29 years, with the exception of 2001. The production level has remained relatively constant around 1300 tonnes during this period. Among EU MS, Germany holds the record for the highest production level of beef meat, surpassing 2100 tonnes in 1991. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that three countries – France, Germany, and Italy – collectively account for more than 50% of the European beef meat volume.

Figure 5. Cumulative annual sheep and goat meat production by EU-27 MS, (1975-2023).
 Source: Authors' compilation based on Eurostat, slaughtering in slaughterhouses - monthly data, data code: apro_mt_pwgtm and apro_mt_pslotm.
 Notes: The MS goat and sheep production is illustrated ordered. The highest values are at the bottom. Goat meat production volume, in 2011 (1826 tonnes) in Italy. This is 291 times higher than 2010 (6,27 tonnes) and 681 times higher than 2012 (2,68 tonnes). We replaced this extreme value by the average value of production levels in 2010 and 2012, which is 4,475 tonnes. Czechia - 2009, Finland - 2023, 2022, 2021, Croatia - 2023, Lithuania - 2023 have missing values for goat meat production.

Figure 5 reports on sheep and goat meat production in EU MS from 1975 to 2023. The y-axis presents the sheep and goat meat production in thousand tonnes (carcass weight), while the x-axis shows the years. Once again, MS are ordered by production volume, with those producing more sheep and goat meat at the bottom of the figure and those producing less at the top.

Sheep and goat meat production has shown an increasing trend from 1975 to 1991 and a decreasing one since 1991. Moreover, the reduction in the meat production takes place gradually. In particular, in the 1990s the total volume of sheep and goat meat production in EU is between 750 and 800 thousand tonnes, whereas in the 2000s is averaged between 700 and 750 thousand tonnes. In 2010s and onwards, the production volume reduces further to 550 – 600 thousand tonnes. Mainly three member states tend to produce more than 50 percent of the total EU volume. In particular, from the late 1980s until 2014, Spain, France and Greece were producing more than 50 percent of the EU total sheep and goat meat production volume and from 2015 and later goat and sheep production in Romania replaced the production in Greece. Interestingly, sheep and goat meat production in Spain has been the highest in EU for 36 years, with exception 2011. Despite of the fact that the Spanish sheep and goat meat production attains the highest volumes in EU every year, the production levels from 2010 and onwards have been reduced approximately by 50 percent compared to the levels of the previous decades. This reduction has significantly contributed also to the reduction of sheep and goat meat production levels in the whole EU.

Overall, in beef, pig and sheep and goat meat production three countries collectively use to account for more than 50% of the European meat volume. In terms of the trends observed in the production

volumes, pig production has shown an upward trend from a decade to the other, sheep and goat meat production has a downward trend from a decade to the other, whereas beef meat production tends to have more stable production levels across time.

2.4. Expected developments in the medium-term

Over the last couple of decades, the demand for meat has been expanding at global level, mainly reflecting an increasing consumption in the case of developing economies. Over the period 2000-2011, global meat demand increased from 209 million tons to 270 million tons in 2011 (1.3 times), while population grew at a slower path (1.1 times). Increasing meat demand has had considerable impacts on feed demand too, which has also been growing during this period (Mitsui Global Strategic Studies, 2016). Nonetheless, it can be expected that meat consumption will reach a peak and stabilise when basic consumer needs are met and other elements such as health issues, animal welfare or some other societal concerns become of importance.

Focusing on the consumption patterns observed in developed countries, Accenture (2017) indicates that more than 50% of consumers are willing to a premium for purchasing products whose production process is committed to certain social and environmental justice criteria. For instance, in the Netherlands, 40% of consumers who joined the 'Week zonder vlees' campaign, which aims at reducing meat consumption claimed environmental reasons as the reason to participate. Moreover, around 34% of the Dutch consumers who joined the campaign indicated animal welfare as their main concern (Boerdam, 2018).⁵ Another important trend that has been identified in developed economies is an increasing number of vegans, vegetarian and flexitarians over the recent past. Nevertheless, the empirical evidence shows that there is a slowdown in the share of consumers adopting these dietary patterns after reaching 20% of the population (Future of meat, 2018).

World Economic Forum (2019) provides an overview of the meat consumption trends that have been registered across different world regions since 1960s, together with a projection for global meat consumption in the coming decades. At global level, meat consumption is expected to follow an upward trend over the period 2020-50. Looking at the regional developments, World Economic Forum (2019) reports a strong increase in meat consumption in China since the mid-1980s, which overcame European levels by mid-1990s.

Within the EU, looking at the historical consumption figures, different patterns can be observed for the 'old' and 'new' Member States, i.e. EU15 and EUN13 regions. Drawing attention to consumption per capita figures, previous Medium-term Outlook (MTO) reports published by DG AGRI suggested that the gap between the two regions could be expected to narrow over time, reaching almost similar levels by 2030.⁶ According to the most recent MTO report published by DG AGRI on January 2024, Figure 6 provides further insights on the evolution of meat consumption per capita for the EU27, by different meat types. Looking at the historical period (2005-2022), meat consumption per capita has remained stable around 67 Kg/person/year, with pig meat representing around 50% of the total meat consumption per capita. For the projection period (2023-35), total meat consumption per capita is expected to annually decline by 0.2%, reaching 65.4 Kg/person/year by 2035.

⁵ From the consumer's perspective, key reasons to reduce meat consumption are health concerns, animal welfare and environmental concerns.

⁶ See, also: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/markets/outlook_en.

Figure 6. EU27 Meat consumption per capita (right axis, bars) and EU27 domestic use (left axis, blue line), (2005-2035).
 Source: Authors’ compilation based on DG AGRI’s medium-term outlook report 2023-2035.
 Notes: r.w.e. stands for retail weight equivalent, while c.w.e. refers to carcass weight equivalent.

Figure 7 reports on the current trends (2005-22) and prospects for the period 2023-35 for meat domestic use, meat net production and meat net trade for the EU27. As shown in the chart, net trade of meat products is expected to remain positive and somehow stable for the period 2023-35. Moreover, meat domestic use and production are expected to slightly decline in the coming decade (with annual rates of growth of around -0.3% and -0.4% respectively).

Figure 7. EU27 meat production and domestic use (right axis) and EU27 meat net trade (left axis), (2005-2035).
 Source(s): Authors’ compilation based on DG AGRI’s medium-term outlook report 2023-2035.

2.5. Selected studies

Table 1 provides an overview of the precise assumptions that have been already modelled in the existing literature when investigating the potential impacts of dietary changes on emissions.

References	Scope	Assumptions modelled in alternative/combined scenarios
Bajželj et al. (2014)	Agriculture and land use change are included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meat intake increases with GDP Increased agricultural yields 50% reduction in food waste Healthy diet
Tilman and Clark (2014)	Agricultural land use change is excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meat intake increases with GDP 15% less meat and fish No meat or fish
Popp et al. (2010)	Scenario for 2055; non-CO ₂ emissions only	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meat intake increases with GDP Meat intake declines by 25% every 10 years Meat intake declines + technology mitigation
Stehfest et al. (2009)	Land-use emissions only	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meat intake increases with GDP 15% less meat No meat No meat, eggs, or dairy
Hedenus et al. (2014)	Excludes agricultural land use change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meat intake increases with GDP 15% less meat[†] 75% less meat and dairy
Westhoek et al. (2014)	Livestock production, feed use, land use and N flows are considered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Replacing 25-50% of animal-derived foods with plant-based foods on a dietary energy basis

Table 1. Literature review – assumptions included in previous studies modelling the impacts of dietary changes on emissions. Source: Adapted from Kim et al. (2015).⁷

2.6. Quantifying the impacts of a dietary change in the EU

Jongeneel et al. (2020) presents the outcomes of a hypothetical sustainable diet scenario which is useful to deliver insights regarding: (i) the increasing consumer awareness about healthy diets and their relation to meat consumption; and (ii) the associated footprint/climate consequences which are highly relevant in view of the Green Deal Roadmap (December 2019) and the Farm to Fork Strategy (May 2020). This scenario is simulated by means of the AGMEMOD-MITERRA modelling system which combines an economic model (AGMEMOD) with a biophysical model (MITERRA-Europe). This modelling system allows us to translate the developments projected for primary agriculture (as calculated by AGMEMOD) into their related environmental impacts (as calculated by MITERRA).

Clustering countries based on per capita meat consumption

Looking at the European continent, FAO (2013) provides an indication about the spatial variation in EU meat consumption. In general terms, there are substantial differences across countries. Looking at the 'extremes', consumption per capita in Spain, Iceland and Austria is above 90 Kg/person, while it is between 70-50 Kg/person in the case of countries such as Estonia, Latvia, Belgium, Romania and

⁷ Kim et al. (2015) define 'healthy diet' as the one 'that limits intake of red meat (max of two 85 g / 3 oz. portions per week), poultry (max of one 85 g / 3 oz. portion per day), dairy, eggs, sugars, and oils to levels recommended by health organizations (e.g., WHO, FAO, American Heart Association, Harvard Medical School), and sets a minimum for fruit and vegetable intake'. The modelling exercise undertaken for Westhoek et al. (2014) also involved the use of the MITERRA-Europe model.

Bulgaria. Moreover, meat consumption is over 70 Kg/person in other countries such as Poland, Norway, Finland and Greece. Higher meat consumption levels (over 80 Kg/person) are observed in France, Germany, the Netherlands and Denmark among others.

Jongeneel et al. (2020) focus on red meat and examine the supply-utilization balances for pork and beef, clustering the EU28 Member States in three categories based on the evolution of consumption per capita in the recent past. More specifically, Table 2 presents further details indicating the regional variation between Member States as well as the observed main trends for both meat types. The number of countries with an increasing trend in per capita consumption during the period 2008-2018 is 11 Member States, with a differentiation by product.

Red meat type	Decreasing cons/cop	Stagnant cons/cap	Increasing cons/cap	Comments
Pig meat	AT, BE, CZ, DK, FR, DE, GR, IE, IT, NL, SK, NL, SK, SL, SW	FI, HU, PL, UK, CY, MT	HR, EE, LV, LT, PT, RO, ES	-3% (-0.32% per annum) From current consumption per capita 39.4 Kg/person to 38.1 Kg/person
Beef	BE, EE, FI, FR, GR, IT, LT, MT, PL, RO, SL, SW, UK, MT, CY	AT, BG, HR, DK, LV, NL, PT, ES	DE, HU, IE, SK	-7% (-0.73% per annum) From current consumption per capita 15.0 Kg/person to 13.9 Kg/person

Table 2. Red meat (apparent) consumption trends in EU, 2008-2018.

Source: Reproduced from Jongeneel et al (2020).

Note: CONS/CAP stands for consumption per capita (Kg/person).

Table 3 provides further insights regarding the consumption levels across the EU28 in order to identify whether there is a linkage between the level and the trend that consumption of red meat have followed over the period 2008-2018. In particular, Member States have been clustered into the following categories: below EU average; around EU average, and above EU average. Since no clear linkage is identified, one can conclude that apart from income other factors such social and cultural preferences matter.

Red meat type	Below average	Around average	Above average	Average 2008-2018
Pig meat	BG, FI, FR, GR, IE, EE, RO, SK, SW, UK, SI, MT	NL, IT, LV	AT, BE, HR, CZ, DK, DE, HU, LT, PL, PT, ES, CY	40.5 Kg/person
Beef	BG, CZ, EE, HU, LV, LT, PL, RO, SK, CY	HR, DE, ES	AT, BE, DK, FI, FR, GR, IE, IT, NL, PT, SI, SW, UK, MT	14.2 Kg/person

Table 3. Comparison of red meat (apparent) consumption patterns in EU, 2008-2018. Source: Reproduced from Jongeneel et al (2020).

Scenario narrative

Jongeneel et al. (2020) conduct an exercise to estimate the share (%) of vegetarian and vegan population in each Member State (Figure 8). As displayed below, the share of vegetarians in 2018 is estimated to be the highest in Germany (about 11% of the population). In contrast, countries such as Bulgaria and Romania are at the lower end, with rates of around 1% or even less.

Figure 8. Share (%) of vegetarian and vegan population (2018 vs 2030). Source: Reproduced from Jongeneel et al (2020).

- In terms of the adoption of a vegetarian diet, the following assumptions in terms of how the number of vegetarians could further increase in the coming decade have been adopted for the purpose of the scenario simulated by Jongeneel et al. (2020): Slow adjustment (0.25% increase/annum) in countries with already a high share of vegetarians (DE, SW, AU, IT, PL); and
- A stronger increase (0.50% increase/annum) in countries have a relative low share of vegetarians (all other EU MS).

Moreover, the scenario presented by Jongeneel et al. (2020) relies on the following assumptions regarding the consumption of red meat, i.e. pork and beef:

- Member States with below average consumption follow their current trend;
- Member States with above average consumption will decline red meat consumption per capita by 1.0% per annum; and

- Member States with average meat consumption will decline red meat consumption by half the amount of 'above', or by 0.5% per annum.

Figure 9 reports on the percentage changes in per capita consumption for beef and pork over the period 2018-2030, resulting from applying the assumptions described above. The figures presented below are the 'final' outcome of combining the following effects: (i) increase in vegetarian population; and (ii) per capita decline due to flexitarians.

Figure 9. Changes (%) in consumption per capita (2018 vs 2030).
Source: Reproduced from Jongeneel et al (2020).

Jongeneel et al. (2020) report that the decline in red meat consumption identified over the period 2008-2018 has been partly 'compensated' by increases consumption of poultry meat and dairy products. For the simulation, Jongeneel et al. (2020) extend the existing patterns into the future. In this study, no explicit assumptions are made regarding the compensation by poultry and dairy products (existing development is assumed to continue unchanged). The already existing trends (for poultry, sheep meat and dairy products consumption) are taken for granted in the simulated scenario. Consumption shocks are assumed to start in 2020. The reader is referred to Jongeneel et al. (2020) for further details on the scenario assumptions.

Scenario results

Drawing attention to the outcomes of AGMEMOD-MITERRA, the following tables/figures provides an overview of the key outcomes of the scenario simulated by Jongeneel et al. (2020). To begin with, Table 4 reports on the expected adjustments in the size of the livestock sector by 2030, resulting from the mentioned change in the dietary preferences of EU consumers (Figure 9). As shown in the table, the dietary change described in the previous section leads to a considerable reduction in the size of the pig sector (-9% compared with 2030 baseline levels).

Livestock units	
Dairy cattle	0.18
Beef cattle	-0.52
Pig	-8.66

Table 4. Results at EU28 level (% deviation from baseline in 2030).
Source: AGMEMOD.

Note: Livestock units for the poultry sector cannot be derived from the AGMEMOD model.

Taking into account the changes in livestock units reported above (Table 4), the expected reductions in organic fertiliser could be derived by applying the relevant excretion factors in a similar way as it is shown in the case study for Switzerland (see, Chapter 4).

According to the simulated scenario, pork production is the meat type for which the largest price decline (around -21%) and production reduction (around -5%) can be expected. Looking at the consumption side, the simulation suggests that beef and pork meat consumption per capita declines by almost 9%, compared with the baseline level.

	Production	Consumption per capita	Average price EU28
Beef	-0.32	-8.95	-1.57
Pork	-4.98	-8.57	-20.80
Poultry	0.04	-0.29	-2.31

Table 5. Results at EU28 level (% deviation from baseline in 2030).

Source(s): AGMEMOD. Adapted from Jongeneel et al. (2020).

In order to translate these production developments into their environmental consequences, the MITERRA-Europe model is used. Table 6 provides an overview of the expected emission reductions for the various pollutants. In this particular scenario, the main source of emission reductions is the decline in pig numbers (see, Table 4). NH₃ emissions could decline by more than 1% compared to the baseline case in which no dietary change is considered.

	Emission reductions
CH ₄ emissions	-0.70
N ₂ O emissions	-0.27
GHG emissions	-0.47
NH ₃ emissions	-1.18
N leaching	-0.31

Table 6. Emissions EU28 (% deviation from baseline in 2030).

Source(s): MITERRA-Europe. Adapted from Jongeneel et al. (2020).

Figure 10 presents a map summarising the changes in GHG (Greenhouse gases) emissions that could be achieved in the simulated scenario. Important regional differences in terms of the expected potential biophysical impacts could be observed. In some Member States like France, the heterogeneity can be observed within the country, e.g. differences in emission reductions between the North-East and the South-West regions. Overall, the transition of the average EU diet towards a more sustainable one will lead to emissions reductions in more than 50% of the European territory (green coloured areas).⁸

⁸ The reader is referred to Jongeneel et al. (2020) for further explanations on the simulated results.

Figure 10. GHG emission agriculture (% change compared to baseline).
Source: MITERRA-Europe. Reproduced from Jongeneel et al. (2020).

2.7. Additional insights at Member State level

In order to supplement the insights delivered by Jongeneel et al. (2020), we refer to a recent study which also employs the AGMEMOD model to simulate the impacts related to a dietary change in the Netherlands. More specifically, Baltussen et al. (2023) examine the social impact of a protein transition preference expressed in money, with Dutch food consumption shifting to 40% animal-based proteins and 60% vegetable proteins by 2030. Moreover, the study investigates the consequences of an additional shift in protein source, reducing total protein consumption by 15%. Table 7 provides an overview of consumption and production impacts in the Netherlands under different scenarios.

Scenario	Consumption ⁹	Production	Comments
Baseline scenario (2030 compared to 2020)	15% less dairy and 18% less meat than current consumption	Large, especially due to decline production of animal protein in the Netherlands and limited increase in grain production	Production mainly continues to decline due to national nitrogen policy
Protein transition scenario 2030	21% less dairy and 52% less meat, 6 times more legumes and 1.85 times more nuts and seeds compared to base scenario 2030	Small decrease compared to basic scenario 2030 of animal protein in the Netherlands	Consumption changes due to protein transition
Protein transition scenario 2030 with reduced protein consumption	33% less dairy and 52% less meat, 2.67 times more legumes and 1.85 times more nuts and seeds compared to base scenario 2030	No impact compared to protein transition scenario 2030	Consumption changes due to protein transition with reduced animal protein consumption (compared to previous scenario)

Table 7. Impacts on food consumption and related production effects in the Netherlands. Source: Adjusted from Baltussen et al. (2023).

3. Case of Switzerland

Here we present the methods and results related to the Switzerland case study. The objective of this study is to analyse how the change in food consumption impacts the entire Swiss food system including agricultural production, manure application for crops, and foreign trade.

3.1. Methods

The model

We use the SWISSfoodSys model to analyse the impacts of dietary changes on the Swiss food system (Figure 11; von Ow et al., 2020). The model is a dynamic mathematical programming model and considers several stages of the food system including agricultural (crop and livestock), processing, trade (export and import), storage and food consumption (nutrition). The model is optimized subject to land area, per capita nutrient consumption requirements, commodity storage capacity, environmental outputs and other constraints. In the model, different stages of the food system are linked, and an optimization process impacts each of these stages. The SWISSfoodSys model includes economic (e.g. production, income, and consumption) and environmental indicators (e.g. GHG emissions and nutrient leaching). Agricultural production includes three regions (mountain, hill and valley) of Switzerland. Crop production includes 40 crops, and livestock types include 40 animal categories. The food demand of consumers is met through per capita nutritional and calorie requirements. We consider 29 macronutrients related to food consumption of the population.

⁹ Consumption figures relates to Dutch population ranging 19-79 years old.

SWISSfoodSys uses data on environmental impacts calculated with the Swiss Agricultural Life Cycle Assessment method (SALCA; Nemecek et al., 2023). SALCA estimates the environmental impacts of food products along the entire food system. The model also includes data from different secondary sources such as Agristat (2018), the Federal Statistical Office (2016), the Federal Customs Administration (2016), and others.

Figure 11. Schematic description of the SWISSfoodSys model.

Scenarios

SWISSfoodSys is first used to simulate the reference scenario, with no diet change scenario and then we addressed impacts of dietary changes of the Swiss population:

- (i) The reference scenario considers current settings of the Swiss food system and does not include any dietary changes. We assume that population increases over years and accordingly total food consumption in Switzerland.
- (ii) To address the impacts of dietary changes of the Swiss population on agricultural production, manure application for crop production, trade, and food consumption, we simulate a scenario that included a change in diet of the Swiss population (Swiss Society for Nutrition 2016) according to the Swiss food pyramid. The Swiss food pyramid includes a combination of different food groups that are recommended to have a nutritional and healthy diet. According to the Swiss food pyramid, consumption of fruits and vegetables must increase, while consumption of meat has to be reduced. Furthermore, we assume that the per capita nutritional consumption requirements must be also met. Similar to the reference scenario, we assume population growth.

The results of the reference and the dietary change scenarios are compared, and to simplify the interpretation of the results, only years 2020, 2025 and 2030 are presented.

3.2. Results

Diet change

The per capita diet does not change over time in the reference scenario (Figure 12). The most consumed products include dairy products and alcoholic beverages (when considered in weight units).

In the diet change scenario, the food consumption of the population is projected to change (Figure 12). Consumption quantities of vegetables, fruits, dairy products and grains substantially increase over the years in contrast to the reference scenario according to the requirements of the Swiss food pyramid model. Particularly, the consumption of vegetables increases by 67% in 2025 and by 124% in 2030 in contrast to the reference scenario. Daily consumption of pulses is 11- and 15-fold larger in

2025 and 2030 respectively than in the reference scenario. However, the absolute consumption quantities of pulses (i.e. in terms of weight in grams) are negligible in the total food basket. In absolute terms, the largest fraction of consumed food consists of dairy products. The recommended food pyramid reduces meat consumption substantially. It is recommended that meat consumption is reduced, and instead consumption and nutritional requirements are replaced by vegetables, fruits, dairy products and grains. Also, the reduction in livestock number reduces meat consumption (see section below Livestock number). Consumption of alcoholic beverages, sweets and fruit juices also decrease in order to comply with the recommended food pyramid.

Figure 12. Food consumption in the reference and diet change scenarios.

Agricultural land-use area

The overall agricultural land-use pattern slightly changes in the reference scenario, which occurs because of food demand increases in relation with population growth (Figure 13). The largest agricultural area is occupied by differently managed meadows like medium-intensive natural meadows, extensive natural meadows, intensive natural meadows and artificial meadows. In contrast, the overall agricultural land-use pattern changes substantially in the diet change scenario. Areas of artificial meadows, intensive meadows natural and medium-intensive meadows, and arable land utilized for fodder are reduced. In contrast, the area of plant-based food crops increases.

Figure 13. Agricultural land use in the reference and diet change scenarios.

Looking into specific crops, the model shows that in relative terms, the area of rye, oat, potato, fruits and vegetables increase substantially (between 2- and 18-folds increase; Figure 14). In absolute terms, the largest increase of 50,000 ha was estimated for wheat which relates to an almost 60% increase in 2030 in comparison to the reference scenario. The areas of grains, potato, fruits and vegetables are higher because of land-use changes from permanent grassland to cropland (i.e. meadows, grains for fodder and maize silage, are replaced by crops that the Swiss food pyramid requirements can be met). The land-use change occurs gradually over years, and the largest changes are observed in 2030. Increase in cropping areas will result also in large calorie values, and reciprocally decrease in cropping areas result in lower calorific and nutritional values and are less required to meet the Swiss food pyramid recommendation.

Figure 14. Crop area in the reference and diet change scenarios.

Livestock number

The livestock number remains constant over years in the reference scenario, except minor changes for some livestock categories, e.g. number of dairy cows (Figure 15). The largest number of livestock include dairy cows, followed by reared cattle for beef production and pigs.

In the diet change scenario, the total livestock number is lower than in the reference scenario and reduced by 15% between 2020 and 2030. The livestock types that mainly decrease are dairy cows, cattle, pigs, fattened chickens and horses. The decrease in the number of these animals is due to a lower consumption of livestock products (e.g. meat) and land-use changes to meet the Swiss recommendation requirements (see sections Diet change and Agricultural land-use area). The livestock number decreases because area of fodder crops reduces.

The number of laying hens, sheep and goat increase as they provide food products to meet nutritional requirements and do not need much fodder from crop cultivation in contrast to livestock types whose number are reduced in the diet change scenario.

Figure 15. Livestock number in the reference and diet change scenarios.

Food self-sufficiency

The results of the SWISSfoodSys simulations show that in the reference scenario the projected increase of the Swiss population leads to an increase of import of food products into Switzerland in order to meet the increased demand for food (Figure 16). Gross and net domestic production and export of food products do not increase over time due to assumed constant resources (e.g. no increase in land area) and absence of technological changes (e.g. no increase in yields) to further increase agricultural production.

In the diet change scenario, net domestic production increases by roughly 24% to meet the food demand of increased population. As a result, the import of food commodities is reduced by about 10%. Moving exclusively to domestic production for food self-sufficiency is not possible for Switzerland because of insufficient suitable land area.

The export of food commodities is assumed to remain constant over the years in both the reference and the diet change scenarios.

Figure 16. Food trade, domestic production and consumption in nutritional energy value in the reference and diet change scenarios.

Organic fertilizer application

In this section, we present results on organic fertilizer supply from livestock manure as a result of dietary changes (Figure 17). In the diet change scenario, total amount of applied manure decreases over the years and the total quantity of manure in 2030 is about 14% lower compared to 2020 (Figure 17a). The large reduction in manure application projected for meadows and other arable areas results from a reduction of the areas of these land uses (see section Agricultural land-use area), whereas manure application for grains increases with the increase in grain crop areas.

In Figure 17b the model results on manure supply by livestock types are presented. The manure for crops mainly comes from cattle (about 80% of total manure), followed by manure from pigs (about 11% of total manure). Manure supply decreases over years as livestock numbers are reduced and less manure is applied to crops.

(a)

(b)

Figure 17. Manure application to crops (a) and supply of manure by livestock types (b).

4. Conclusions

This study provides some insights regarding the dietary changes that have occurred/are currently occurring in the EU and beyond. Secondly, our study uses the economic simulation model SWISSfoodSys to analyse the impacts of a dietary changes on the Swiss food system. This case study shows that the change in food diet impacts the entire food system including agricultural production, processing and trade. As a result, the population diet changes with a substantial consumption shift towards vegetables, fruits and grains, while consumption of meat and alcoholic beverages substantially declines. These changes impact the land-use pattern where the area of grains, vegetables and fruits increase, while the area of crop fodder and meadows is reduced. The total livestock number also declines to meet the food pyramid requirement.

The results of this study can help to understand how changing diets of the population can impact agricultural production, as well as their environmental consequences. The study also provides insights that can be useful for policy-making when developing policies to support those farmers who could be negatively affected in view of the changes in diets in the countries under consideration. For example, in the Swiss case study, change in diets reduce demand for livestock products and accordingly livestock numbers, which might require government support for livestock rearing farmers to maintain their incomes or in transitioning to other farming activities.

5. Future research

The work presented in this report can be extended in the future. Firstly, the research team is currently further developing and extending the structure and database of the SWISSfoodSys model. For example, the model extensions that the team will conduct include the implementation of indicators to assess the impacts of food consumption on human health, as well as the introduction of new variables to deliver projections of food consumption by population groups, and different environmental indicators to simulate impacts along the food system. Including these different components into the model can provide a better understanding on the impacts of changing human diets on the food system. Secondly, the additional qualitative insights presented in the EU case could be used as alternative scenario assumptions to be explored by means of the modelling system 'AGMEMOD-MITERRA'.

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